

Maksym Rokmaniko, Mykola Holovko

SPATIAL RECONSTRUCTION OF BABYN YAR

Максим Рохманійко, Микола Головка

ПРОСТОРОВА РЕКОНСТРУКЦІЯ БАБИНОГО ЯРУ

This paper presents a spatial reconstruction of Babyn Yar aimed at clarifying the debated locations of the mass shootings of Kyiv's Jews on September 29–30, 1941. We combine three methodological blocks: (1) the construction of a high-precision digital elevation model based on the 1924 topographic survey, using TIN interpolation and Delaunay triangulation; (2) the georeferencing of German aerial photographs to the terrain model with optical distortion correction; and (3) the photogrammetric localization of historical ground photographs in 3D space. The cross-referencing of the digital terrain model, aerial imagery, and ground photography allows for a better understanding of the historical landscape of Babyn Yar, a critical assessment of previous reconstruction attempts, and the precise localization of several key photographs by Johannes Hähle, delineating the area of executions along the western spur of the ravine. The proposed methodological framework ensures analytical reproducibility and establishes a robust foundation for future historical-geographical research and memory preservation practices.

Keywords: spatial reconstruction, Babyn Yar, Holocaust in Ukraine, Digital elevation model (DEM), Historical geography, Photogrammetry, aerial imagery, memory studies.

Стаття пропонує просторову реконструкцію Бабиного Яру, покликану уточнити дискусійні локації масових розстрілів 29–30 вересня 1941 р. Ми поєднуємо три блоки методів: (1) побудову високоточної цифрової моделі рельєфу на основі топоїмки 1924 р. із застосуванням TIN-інтерполяції та триангуляції Делоне; (2) геоприв'язку німецьких аерофотознімків до моделі місцевості з корекцією оптичних спотворень; (3) фотограмметричну локалізацію історичних кадрів у 3D-просторі. Зіставлення цифрового рельєфу, аерознімків та наземної зйомки дозволяє краще зрозуміти історичну місцевість Бабиного Яру, оцінити попередні спроби реконструкції, аргументовано локалізувати низку ключових фотографій Йоганнеса Гьоле й окреслити зону місць розстрілів уздовж західного відрозу Бабиного Яру. Запропонований комплекс методів забезпечує відтворюваність аналізу та створює основу для подальших історико-географічних досліджень і практик збереження пам'яті.

Ключові слова: просторова реконструкція, Бабин Яр, Голокост в Україні, цифрова модель рельєфу, історична географія, фотограмметрія, аерофотознімки, студії пам'яті.

At the time when this spatial reconstruction study began, in 2021, two competing hypotheses were discussed regarding the location of the Babyn Yar mass shootings on September 29–30, 1941. One group of scholars relied mostly on eyewitness testimonies – led by Vitaliy Nakhmanovych and Tetiana Yevstafieva, – located the site close to the present-day Dorohozhychi metro station, near the Soviet-era memorial to the victims of Babyn Yar (Yevstafieva & Nakhmanovych, 2004, Appendix 32). Other scholars, following the work of Ilya Levitas and Lev Drobiazko, argued that the site of the massacre was situated approximately one kilometer further north (Drobiazko, 2003). Looking at earlier attempts

to locate the mass shootings, there are additional, even more contradictory theories regarding the locations (Kalnytskyi & Paskevych, 1999, p. 12; Malakhov, 2001). Given the historical significance of this site, it may appear surprising that its exact location remains contested. However, closer examination of the site's history renders this uncertainty more comprehensible.

In the postwar years, public documentation and commemoration of the 1941 mass shootings at Babyn Yar were shaped by censorship and a universalizing rhetoric that downplayed the specifically Jewish character of the killings (Berkhoff, 2009; Clowes, 2005; Zeltser, 2012). Attempts by local activists and

Jewish intellectuals to commemorate the victims – such as the 1966 and 1969 gatherings at the site – were suppressed by police and the KGB, resulting in what Oleksandr Ihnatenko (2023) calls a «state-engineered amnesia». This systematic suppression of historical specificity and control over public space exemplifies the politics of silence that characterized Soviet responses to the Holocaust in Ukraine.

Beyond the context of Soviet memory politics, the physical landscape where the events took place has been radically transformed. The word *yar* literally means «ravine» in Ukrainian, a geomorphological formation typically shaped by the erosive movement of water flowing toward a river. Through large-scale earthworks undertaken in the late 1950s and early 1960s, Babyn Yar was filled with liquid soil, resulting in the near-total disappearance of the ravine itself (Drobiazko & Khorunzhaia, 2003). Highways were constructed over the newly flattened area, as well as residential buildings, and the park. The area has thus been altered so extensively that the difficulty of determining the precise locations of the events of 1941 is rather unsurprising.

When examining previous attempts to map the territory of Babyn Yar, beginning in the late 1960s, it becomes clear that most studies were undertaken in response to construction projects planned on or near

the site. In 1969, such a study was commissioned by the State Construction Committee of the Ukrainian SSR, partly involving survivors of Babyn Yar such as Dina Pronicheva – motivated by plans to develop the area (Nakhmanovych, 2004, p. 52). In 1999, amid the construction of the Dorohozhychi metro station, the *Historical and Urban Development Reference Plan of the Babyn Yar Territory* was prepared by Kyivproekt, with the «historical note» underpinning this document was written by the local historian Mykhailo Kalnytskyi. In the early 2000s, public debates arose around the proposed construction of the *Spadschyna* («Heritage») Center, once again bringing the unresolved territory of Babyn Yar into the spotlight by activating attempts to map the events of 1941, particularly reconstructions by Levitas and Drobiazko. In their assessment, Yevstafieva and Nakhmanovych indicate that many of these positions were affected by the construction projects themselves, where scholars would use questionable – by scholarly standards – testimonies «to avoid a potential scandal» (Yevstafieva & Nakhmanovych, 2004, p. 55).

In 2004, Yevstafieva and Nakhmanovych published their volume *Babyn Yar: Liudyna, Vlada, Istoriiia*, which systematically reviewed previous studies and assembled dozens of eyewitness

Fig. 1. Babyn Yar in 1943 (left) and in 2022 (right), before and after its flattening

Fig. 2. Topographic survey panel № 434 by City Communal Services Department (Горкоммуналдзла) from 1924

testimonies. Their analysis was notably *multimodal*, combining different primary sources: drawings, documents, photographs, and testimonies, and reading them against one another (Kress, 2010, p. 1). In one chapter, Dmytro Malakov provides a detailed commentary on the photographs taken by a propaganda photographer Johannes Hähle, most likely captured a few days after the massacre (Malakov, 2004, p. 164). He analyzes them one by one, mentally reconstructing the path of the photographer through the site of mass executions.

Appendices 28 and 30 of the volume already show the initial steps toward digital spatial modeling. Nakhmanovych writes: «The availability of both topographic plans of the area and original photo-documents makes it possible to attempt comparative analysis using three-dimensional computer modeling methods» (Yevstafieva & Nakhmanovych, 2004, p. 12). This early experiment is an important precedent for this study, although the spatial reconstruction remained a secondary aspect of their study, and some of its spatial placements – such as the

Fig. 3. Tracing topographic lines from pre-processed archival drawings

Fig. 4. Transformation of original raster survey (left) to level inversion (center), and, further, to vectorized contour lines (right)

Fig. 5. Elevated digitized contour lines

Fig. 6. Digital elevation model of Babyn Yar as of 1948

Fig. 7. Digital elevation model of Babyn Yar as of 2018

Fig. 8. Collection of German reconnaissance footage from 1939, 1941, 1943, and 1944

Fig. 9. Stereoscopic image pairs used for terrain photogrammetry and lens distortion correction

Fig. 10. Topographic maps and aerial images are aligned using buildings from the 1920s that still stand today as reference points

modeled location of one of Hähle's photographs in Appendix 30, as we will demonstrate in this paper – proved inaccurate.

The challenge of understanding the lost wartime topography of Babyn Yar remains relevant today. Building on these earlier efforts, our contribution is threefold. First, we constructed a high-fidelity digital elevation model (DEM) of the Babyn Yar terrain based on topographic maps from the 1920s. Second, we overlaid this model with a range of aerial photographs taken by the Luftwaffe in the 1940s. And third, we assembled and analyzed dozens of photographs and film fragments from Babyn Yar, locating them against the digital terrain, using an image-matching algorithm. Together, these materials constitute what Eyal Weizman (2017, p. 186) describes as an *architectural-image-complex* – an assemblage of diverse media artifacts systematically organized in relation to a spatial 3D model. This assemblage answers some of the previously debated questions, such as the location, where Hähle's photographs were taken, and provides a reusable analytic corpus for subsequent historical work on Babyn Yar.

The City Communal Services Department (Горкоммуналдел) topographic survey of Babyn Yar from 1924 (Fig. 2) served as the primary source for generating the site's digital elevation model. The survey sheets were high-resolution scanned and

processed using software packages, such as *QGIS*, *AutoCAD*, *Blender*, and *Grasshopper for Rhinoceros 3D*. To prepare the maps for digitization, colour filters were applied to isolate contour lines, and extraneous graphic elements were removed. The cleaned raster images were then imported into a CAD environment, where each contour line was vectorized and assigned its corresponding elevation value, using Bitonal tracing mode in *AutoCAD* (Fig. 3).

The spatial model then was constructed using a Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN) interpolation method. In *QGIS*, this was performed using the TIN Interpolation tool. In *Rhinoceros/Grasshopper*, the terrain surface was generated using *Delaunay triangulation*, followed by the projection of a square mesh grid onto the resulting surface (McNeel & Associates, 2021) (Fig. 6).

This workflow enabled the precise reconstruction of a three-dimensional elevation model of the historical landscape of Babyn Yar. Later the same methodology was applied to trace topographic maps from 1948, 1952 and 2018.

The second key step in this spatial reconstruction was to georeference the elevation model with German aerial reconnaissance photographs from the 1940s (Fig. 8). Originally produced for reconnaissance purposes, these images now serve as unique historical records of the Babyn Yar terrain prior to the postwar flattening and obliteration. The aerials were sourced

Fig. 11. Digital elevation model, overlaid with the aerial photograph from 1943

from the National Archives and Records Administration (NARA), Record Group 373 (NAID 44236464) in Washington, D.C.

The aerial photographs exhibit noticeable lens distortion. To project them correctly onto the digital terrain, we used photogrammetric tools to estimate each image's camera pose and lens-distortion parameters (Fig. 9). After calibration, the original images were orthorectified and draped over the DEM-derived 3D terrain model, then aligned with contemporary satellite imagery using long-standing buildings from the 1920s as ground control points (GCPs) (Fig. 10). This workflow ensures that historical imagery aligns accurately with the modern landscape, providing a reliable basis for further analysis and reconstruction (Fig. 11).

As the final step in reassembling the historic terrain of Babyn Yar, we located archive imagery in 3D space using an image-matching workflow (Center for Spatial Technologies, 2024). This method helps better understand the historic terrain, by showing how the terrain would have appeared from specific points of view.

We worked with a diverse range of photographic materials, gathering images from multiple archives, tracking down originals, and carefully excluding pictures not taken at Babyn Yar (which were

surprisingly common in generic web searches for «Babyn Yar»). In particular, we focused on the photographs taken by the Nazi propaganda photographer Johannes Hähle, numbered 6, 7, 16, 17, and 18 (Fig. 12), held at the Hamburg Institute for Social Research. The photographs were analyzed and grouped by terrain features (Fig. 13).

Several 1940s photographs – including frames 16, 17, and 18 from Johannes Hähle's film – feature a hill with V-shaped vegetation cover; it is clearly identifiable in our digital model (Fig. 14). By matching the viewing angle to this landform, we positioned a virtual camera within the 3D model to reproduce the terrain view observed in each photograph, thereby reconstructing the exact camera position (see Fig. 16 as an example of this). These three photographs – which are commonly interpreted as depicting the area of the mass shootings of Kyiv's Jews on September 29–30, 1941 – prove to be taken along the western spur of Babyn Yar, corroborating the hypothesis of Levitas and Drobiazko (Fig. 17), and proving wrong the aforementioned reconstruction by Nakhmanovych.

However, some important historic photographs did not have easily identifiable terrain features, which made locating them much more difficult. Hähle's photographs numbered 6 and 7, show a flat area with

Fig. 12. Photo film by Johannes Hähle. Photographs numbered 6–18 are taken in Babyn Yar.
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a large amount of clothing and other personal belongings of Babyn Yar victims scattered on the ground (Fig. 15). To find the location of these photographs, we first located two fragments of video footage from 1943, as well as a photograph that features both the previously located hill and the scattered clothing from the mass shootings (Fig. 16). Thus, we were able to verify the hypothesis first posited by Malakhov that photos 6 and 7 were taken in the area of a former sand quarry, north of contemporary Dorohozhychi metro station (Malakhov, 2004, p. 167).

Our initial photo-matching was performed manually by placing a virtual camera in the 3D model and aligning its view to landscape configurations

visible in historical photographs. To reduce error and determine exact camera poses on high-fidelity terrain, we then developed an algorithmic solution as a Blender add-on (Center for Spatial Technologies, 2024). Image matching algorithm aligns 2D images to a 3D model using the *perspective-n-point method*, solving for camera extrinsics (position, orientation) and intrinsics (focal length, principal point, lens distortion) and positioning the camera in virtual space with a much higher level of precision. This way we were able to reconstruct the exact locations where Hähle took five photographs from his film, and pinpoint these locations against the historic terrain, as well as the contemporary map (Fig. 17).

Fig. 13. Identification of the key terrain features on photographs numbered 16 and 17 from the Johannes Hähle film

Fig. 14. The hill with V-shaped vegetation cover on archive photographs, as well as on the spatial model of Babyn Yar

Fig. 15. Closeups of photographs numbered 6 and 7 from the Johannes Hähle film, overlaid with marked common terrain features

Fig. 16. Closeups of photographs numbered 6 and 7 from the Johannes Hähle film, overlaid with marked common terrain features

Fig. 17. Contemporary satellite imagery overlaid with the historic landscape of Babyn Yar. The locations of the historic photographs are marked, with arrows indicating camera direction. Markers 1 and 2 correspond to frames 6 and 7 from Johannes Haehle's film and show the former sand quarry where victims were forced to undress before the shootings. Markers 3, 4, and 5 correspond to frames 16, 17, and 18, respectively, and depict Soviet prisoners of war covering the shooting site, guarded by Waffen SS

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Рохманійко Максим Олександрович, дослідник, директор, Центр просторових технологій, Київ, Україна.
Rokmaniko Maksym, Researcher, Director, Center for Spatial Technologies, Kyiv, Ukraine.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8001-3946>

E-mail: maksym@spatialtech.info

Головко Микола Миколайович, дослідник, Центр просторових технологій, Київ, Україна.
Holovko Mykola, Researcher, Center for Spatial Technologies, Kyiv, Ukraine.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-1759-7248>

E-mail: mykola@spatialtech.info

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